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Research Article

**CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH STUDY TO FIND-OUT
ISSUES WITH BABIES HAVING LOW ATTIE BIRTH AND
HYPER-TENSION AFTER SURVEY [AS] DURING 4-14 YEARS**¹Dr. Tayyaba Ibrahim, ²Muhammad Asad Zia, ³Dr. Shamsa Shafique¹Children Hospital Lahore²Jinnah Hospital Lahore³Services Hospital Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: This research study was held to find-out issues with babies having low weight at the birth and hyper-tension after Atabrine sterilisation [AS] during 4-14 years survey from February, 2006 to February, 2016 in Lahore.

Study Design: The research study was held as sampling.

Duration and Place of Study: In this study the females having trans-cervical attachment of Atabrine during 2006-2016, Lahore were included. The period for this study was March, 2013-May, 2014.

Method: The size of tester was designed at 96% and self-confidence level was 541. Selection method was simple casual selection. The home-home study for Atabrine Sterilisation has completed with the help of female health-workers, completed already designed questionnaires. Referral & scrutiny was carried out at the General Hospital Lahore.

Results: The mean-age at Atabrine Sterilisation was 39Y, which was calculated with measurements and incident circulation, typical fluctuation 8.231, typical error=0.462. The statistics aspects demonstrate that the most of the women were living in [rustic areas] 68%, [jobless] 89.8%, [poor] 52.02% and [illiterates] 66%. In the research baby birth with low weight were in 9 [1.67%] and hyper-tension was in [114] 21.0% female later atabrine sterilisation.

Conclusion: Baby birth with low weight and hyper-tension were stated in women after atabrine sterilisation. Therefore, these conclusions may have an attitude on everlasting atabrine practices and strategy for future surveys.

Key words: Still births, Atabrine Sterilisation, before time births, birth flaws.

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INTRODUCTION:

In our research Atabrine Sterilisation was presented in chille by zipper and his coworkers [1]. During study tried numerous causes on observational agents and assessed the special effects management for Atabrine in women [2]. During 1970 Atabrine in more than 34 countries was for women Sterilisation all over the world. Presence of Atabrine was used for many-years to yield fibrosis in-serosa and omentum cavities [3]. Our technique was acknowledged as an everlasting procedure in publics of contraception. Meantime, some content for Atabrine Sterilisation was informed some issues like fetal malformations hyper-tension, ectopic pregnancy, and low weight birth of baby [4]. An alarm was elevated about the side effects of Atabrine Sterilisation [5]. The investigation studies displayed that there are none major signs of amplified risk for generative region for cancers of Atabrine Sterilisation procedures [6]. In Pakistan Atabrine Sterilisation was presented in Lahore by professor Aqeel Ali in 2006 at General Hospital. Through 1990 efforts were ready to teach the women about family preparation procedures comprising the overview of Atabrine Sterilisation in Lahore. A review in February 1991 of 1000 married female displayed preventative occurrence [43.3%] with [19%] with long-lasting women sterilisation [7]. During study it was revealed that multi-parity, early marriages and low socioeconomic status were pointedly linked with amplified material mortality. The family preparation procedures and particularly sterilisation procedures could decrease maternal sickness and humanity. In Lahore the women sterilization procedures prospered who was bringing mortality material was under countrywide average [8]. After making observations related Atabrine Sterilisation, the cases regarding old style were forwarded to CMH Lahore. In this research about 11001 cases of Atabrine women sterilisation were studied and there was very low number of death, birth flaws and cancers were reported. Thus, birth with low weight and before time births were originates. Therefore, in Lahore it was observed that the biggest particular enclosure of Atabrine Sterilisation [9]. Investigation study created by University of Health Sciences Lahore was discovered indications related to hyper-tension and heart infection in cities public which is more than the village public. However, while making comparison of female to male, it was observed that female having greater risks of heart disease. In this study it was revealed that the highest rate of reported prolonged female related disease was displayed highest load of sickness due to hyper-tension [10]. The occurrences related to familial alteration, hypertension and low weight baby birth was defined Atabrine sterilized

women however, particular woman was not analytical noteworthy. Therefore, in this research was showed and define baby's birth with low weight and hypertension after trans-cervical insertion of atabrine for women Sterilisation in Lahore from 6-17 years pursue of atabrine placing during 2006 to 2016.

METHODOLOGY:

Our research report was carried-out in Lahore on the base of sampling. In this study the women trans-cervical inclusion with Atabrine from 2006 to 2016 were involved for analysis. Atabrine sterilized women record had gotten from 5 healthcare centers of Lahore.

The selected healthcare centres were as follows:

Shamim Clininc Mother & Child Health Center Township Lahore.

Umair Mother and Child Care Clinic Shama Road Lahore.

Mother Saved Child Clinic Karim Park Lahore.

Mother and child clinic Johar Town Lahore.

Mother and Child Health Clinic Aziz Bhati Town Lahore.

While study the model size was designed through Epi info 2000. The atabrine sterilised women populace was 10000 during 1994 to 2004. In atabrine sterilisation the predictable frequency of sterilization failure was noted 6.3%18. Therefore, the worst suitable results were 8.5%. In research self-assurance level was 543 and sample size was calculated at 96%. Sampling technique was simple taking random casual sampling. During study decent problems were lectured and related material was reserved as private. From all the participants advised permission was taken. Therefore, those women were not included in the study which were declined to give permission. The survey about Atabrine Sterilisation has prepared with the help of lady workers. Atabrine sterilised women who was falling presence & omission affection were encouraged for further treatment in Mother and child clinic Johar Town Lahore. Data collection was done by the already steted and designed proforma. In this study taking 4 sequential checkups of blood pressure after 6 hours one by one and noted the pressure of blood was 145/102 was declared the reason of hyper-tension. During the analysis taking mean values and it was revealed that the women who have normal blood pressure were preceding treatment of anti-hypertension. During study it was observed that the baby with low weight birth was having weight low from 1.9 kilogram at birth. Epi-info 2000 was used for data analysis. The mean, frequency, standard deviations and percentage were calculated for measureable variables. The

stratification of data as per duration and age of atabrine sterilisation was done to control confounders.

RESULTS:

After 6 to 17 years of atabrine sterilisation the total women who were monitored were 542. The period calculation and dissemination of figures showed

average at Atabrine Sterilisation is 39Years, typical error 0.502 and deviation was 6.780. In demo-graphic types features displayed females of Atabrine Sterilisation are living in rural areas [70%], Illiteracy [66%], poverty [55.50%] and un-employed [92.8%]. Details are mentioned below in table-1: -

Table1. Demographic features of female atabrine sterilisation.

Variable		Percentage	Quantity
Poverty	Yes	51.85%	280
	No	48.15%	260
Literacy	Literate	35.1%	189
	Illiterate	64.9%	351
Employment	Employed	10.93%	59
	Unemployed	89.07%	481
Residence	Rural	67%	362
	Urban	33%	178
Age at atabrine sterilisation	34 years or less	19.6%	106
	More than 35yrs	80.3%	434

During research it was revealed that hyper-tension 115 [23.25] and baby with low weight 10 [2.23%] in female atabrine sterilisation. Details are mentioned below in table-2: -

Table2. Frequency distribution and percentages of study variables

Variable	Hyper-tension		Pregnancy		Duration of Atabrine sterilisation			Birth with low weight	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	10 less	Years or	More than 10	Yes	No
Percentage	23.25%	81.1%	11.23%	92%	87.54%		16.25%	2.23%	99.33%
Frequency	115	430	58	482	503		95	10	545

DISCUSSION:

While study was in process it was noticed that, Atabrine Sterilisation was reported from Lahore, Pakistan. Therefore, there were a large number of cases with Atabrine Sterilisation was reported in municipal [5]. Though, during this research it was noticed that the extensive tenure is required for complete examination and provide proof for its secure use and effectiveness. Our research's at atabrine sterilisation average age is 39years, standard error 0.502 and standard deviation was 6.780. Sokal and sahadia had defined atabrine sterilisation in women having average age 34years, standard deviation 11.35 and average age 38 years, standard deviation 8.35 correspondingly [6, 7]. Therefore, the younger age women were included in our study. In

our research study after atabrine sterilisation different side-effects were noted in women like birth with low weight in 10 [2.23%] and hyper-tension in 115 [23.25%]. During continue treatment of Atabrine Sterilisation an-other study was reported the same adverse effects [8]. In ethnic subgroups the age standardized prevalence displayed that Balochi 43.3% women and 27.5% men, in Punjabi 20% women and 19.5% men, in Pashtun 30.5% women and 36.5% men, Sindhi 12.6% women and 23.3% men, in Muhajir 27.6% women and 28.3% were hyper-tensive¹³. In our research study 23.25% incidence of hyper-tension was stated in atabrine sterilization in Punjab, which was greater than 20% in Punjabi women. In this study the babies birth with low weight were found in 2.23% females. However,

in one other research it was noticed that the mean weight of the new born babies was 3.23Kg. It was noticed that 77% babies weight ranged from 2.5kg to 4kg, 5% of weight above 4 kg and 18% had low weight at the time of birth. In this it was reported that out 1230 babies birth with low weight 17% were delayed growth, 72% were preterm and 11% were both premature and delayed growth [10]. In this study revealed the reasons for babies with low weight were pre-matured birth, cooperative {>5}, parental progressive age [>35years]. Alike findings were also noticed in other research. For observing development towards reducing mortalities and infant diseases data regarding birth weight were essential. Also in another research it was revealed that 4300 babies were studied who born in Mid City Hospital Lahore, out of which 450 were with low weight at birth and 200 admitted in nursery for treatment. It was further noticed that the ratio between men and women was observed 1.20:2.30 [240women, 210men]. About 18.9% of Preterm babies and babies with the weight less 2kgs were 43% of total babies with low at birth. From 191 babies, 16[8.3%] had respiratory syndrome of newly born baby, 12[6.2%] had hypocalcemia, 16 [18.3%] had vomiting, 99[51.8%] had hyperbilirubinemia, 10 [5.3%] had objective disease, 16[8.3%] vomiting. General reasons of indisposition in {WLB} babies were sepsis, hypoglycemia, hypothermia, suffering breathing disease and jaundice [11]. Results as discuss were also described in meta-scrutiny. There are 86 studies which were documented the results of weight low babies. During research it was revealed that 44%infant were $\leq$ 1500g, 29% were $\leq$ 1000g and 27% infants were $\leq$ 2500g. The conclusion worsened with low weight births and also found statistically important [16]. Improvements in technology and medicine had improved the care capability at early gestations for babies. Around has a change to previous gestational, therefore the variations made a problem for untimely birth of baby. Whenever, babies have born untimely then the ratios for diseases has increased about advance births. It was observed that in all over the world, our country contained a large number of babies with low weightage. Therefore, in the study described that birth with low weight should not be ignored. In our country Pakistan, Atabrine women Sterilisation has executed in a large number. Therefore, the continue appointments of Atabrine Sterilised women should stimulated and material related to defects must be in approach of common people. Additionally, trainings and survey reports should be planned to relate the long-lasting Sterilisation procedures for better community health.

CONCLUSION:

According to resultant statistics of the current study it was found that baby birth with low weight and hypertension were established Atabrine Sterilisation female. Therefore, these conclusions may have a bearing on everlasting Sterilisation performs and proposal of future.

REFERENCES:

1. World Health Organization. Mechanism of action, safety and efficacy of intrauterine devices. WHO Tech Rep Ser 1987; 753:1–91
2. Bashir A, Cheema MA, Akram S, Naheed R. Quinacrine nonsurgical female sterilization. The Gynaecologist 1993; 3:129–136.
3. Bashir A, Bashir M, Afzal S. The effect of special training for quinacrine sterilization in Faisalabad Pakistan: a report on 1833 women subset of 11,000 cases. International Journal of Gynaecology and obstetrics 2003; 83:67-73.
4. Khabir Ahmad, Tazeen H. Jafar. Prevalence and determinants of blood pressure screening in Pakistan. Journal of Hypertension 2005;23(11):1979-84
5. Bashir A. Refresher courses of Traditional Birth Attendants. JPMA 1982; 32(7):168–169.
6. Suhadia, M. Anwarb, A, Soejoenoes A. 10-year follow-up of women who elected quinacrine sterilization (QS) in Wonosobo, Central Java, Indonesia. International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics 2003; 83:137–139.
7. Sokal DC, Zipper J, King T. Transcervical quinacrine sterilization: clinical experience. Int J Gynecol Obstet 1995; 51: S57–S69.
8. Hieu DT, Tan TT, Tan DN. Maternal and Child Health/Family Planning Department, Ministry of Health, Hanoi, Vietnam. 31,781 cases of non-surgical female sterilisation with quinacrine pellets in Vietnam. Lancet 1993;342(8865):213–7.
9. Jafar TH, Levey AS, Jafary FH. Ethnic subgroup differences in hypertension in Pakistan. J Hypertens 2003; 21:905–12
10. Naimi RS. Distribution of birth weights of hospital born Pakistani infants. JPMA 2000; 4:42-5.
11. Zaidi KA, Aijaz N, Nasr-ul-Huda. Low birth weight babies; frequently encountered problems at secondary level care. Professional Med J 2013;20(2): 193-198.
12. Aylward GP, Pfeiffer SI, Wright A, Verhulst SJ. Outcome studies of low birth weight infants published in the last decade: A metaanalysis. The Journal of Pediatrics 1989;115(4):515-20.
13. Zipper J, Cole LP, Goldsmith A, Wheeler R, Rivera M. Quinacrine hydrochloride pellets:

- preliminary data on a nonsurgical method of female sterilization. *Int J GynaecolObstet* 1980; 18:275-279.
14. Shannon JA, Earle DP, Jr, Brodie BB, Taggart JV, Berliner RW. The pharmacological basis for the rational use of atabrine (quinacrine) in treatment of malaria. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 1944; 81:307-330
 15. Kessel E, Zipper J, Mumford SD. Quinacrine nonsurgical female sterilization: a reassessment of safety and efficacy. *Fertil Steril* 1985; 44:293-298.
 16. Fitzhugh OG, Nelson AA, Calvary HO. The chronic toxicity of quinacrine. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 1945; 85:207-221.